

THE APPLICABILITY OF LEAD AMALGAM ELECTRODES IN THE ESTIMATION OF Pb^{++} , SO_4^{--} , AND Ba^{++} BY POTENTIOMETRIC TITRATION

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A two-phase lead amalgam electrode under ordinary experimental conditions has been found to be applicable in the estimation of Pb^{++} , Ba^{++} and SO_4^{--} from the aqueous solutions of their salts mixed with suitable quantities of ethyl alcohol, by potentiometric titration with standard solutions of sodium oxalate, sodium sulphate and lead nitrate.

It has been observed by many early investigators that in the absence of oxygen lead behaves as a reversible electrode. The values of the standard electrode potential obtained by different workers (Getman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 792; Lewis and Brighton, *ibid.*, 1917, 39, 1906) differed a good deal. Puschin (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1903, 36, 201) was the first to point out that all two-phase lead amalgams having percentage of lead between 1.8% and 66% exhibited the same electromotive force. Henderson and Stegeman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1918, 40, 84) confirmed this from 2.5% to 6%. Gerke (*ibid.*, 1922, 44, 1684) used an amalgam containing 5% of lead in his experiments and confirmed reproducibility. Bray (*ibid.*, 1927, 49, 2374) confirmed the observation of the previous workers that presence of oxygen in the electrolyte vitiated the experiments. Hatfield and Zapponi (*Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1939, 75, 473) also testified to the reproducibility of the lead electrode.

Kolthoff and Furman ("Potentiometric Titrations", Wiley and Sons, 1931, p. 65) working with low concentration of lead ions did not find lead electrode to be reproducible. A reversible lead electrode was obtained by using ferrocyanide-ferricyanide redox system along with lead salt. This electrode was used by Muller and co-workers (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1923, 62, 29; 1927, 72, 1195) in the titration of lead. Sulphate was estimated by adding an excess of lead nitrate, filtering off the precipitate and titrating back with ferrocyanide after the addition of alcohol. This method, according to Kolthoff, is not convenient. Similar attempts were made by Zhukov and Raikhinstein (*J. Gen. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1934, 4, 962) and Shakhkeldian (*J. Appl. Chem. U. S. S. R.*, 1937, 10, 1706; 1938, 11, 56) for the estimation of SO_4^{--} and Pb^{++} . These methods, according to Kolthoff (*loc. cit.*) and Maheswari and Jha (*this Journal*, 1937, 14, 42), suffer from many disadvantages.

The possibility of the use of lead electrodes in the determination of Ca^{++} using a system such as $Pb/PbSO_4$, $CaSO_4$, Ca^{++} was first postulated by Luther (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1898, 27, 364). Such an electrode is usually referred to as an electrode of the third order. The suitability of such electrodes in potentiometric titrations was shown by LeBlanc and Harnapp (*ibid.*, 1923, 166, 321) who also developed its theory adequately. Velisek (*Chem. Listy*, 1930, 24, 443, 467; 1933, 27, 3) studied the Luther electrode as well as Pb/PbC_2O_4 , CaC_2O_4 , Ca^{++} and $Pb/Pb(IO_3)_2$, $Ca(IO_3)_2$, Ca^{++} and

observed that there were many complications which reduced their value as a suitable electrode for the estimation of Ca^{++} . Denina and Caris (*Gazzetta*, 1938, 68, 293) however, observed that Pb (dil. amalgam)/ PbC_2O_4 , CaC_2O_4 , Ca^{++} was very stable and had a sensitivity of measurement of 0.1 mV. Moreover, the presence of chloride ions did not interfere appreciably. These workers do not appear to have carried out further researches on the lead amalgam electrode, although they held that it possessed electrochemical properties of great advantage.

In this paper are recorded the results obtained by using lead amalgam electrode in the estimation of lead as sulphate, oxalate and chromate, that of sulphate as lead and barium sulphate and the estimation of barium as sulphate using the electrode Pb (sat. amalgam.), PbSO_4 , Ba^{++} . The titrations have been carried out in water and water-alcohol solutions. Two forms of the electrode vessels have been found to be suitable and are shown in Fig. 1

E X P E R I M E N T A L

A two-phase amalgam was prepared by the electrolysis of a 10% lead nitrate solution with a mercury cathode, the anode being a Pt-foil dipped in nitric acid contained in a separate beaker and connected with the former by means of an inverted U-tube containing the same acid. A current of about 50 milliamp. was passed for a period of time sufficient to give an approximately 5% amalgam. The amalgam was washed free of the acid with distilled water and acetone, dried in a vacuum and stored in a nitrogen atmosphere.

The reference electrode chosen was saturated calomel half-cell with the siphon limb dipping into saturated KCl solution. The salt-bridge connecting the latter with the solution in the titration vessel was made with a gel of 3% agaragar containing KNO_3 as the conducting electrolyte.

The reagents used were of A. R. quality and the usual precautions were taken in preparing their solutions. These solutions were standardised by the usual methods: lead nitrate, sodium sulphate and barium chloride gravimetrically as the sulphates of lead and barium, while potassium chromate was estimated volumetrically, according to the methods of Treadwell and Hall (*"Analytical Chemistry"*, Vol II, 1945). Sodium oxalate was taken as a primary standard, the purity factor having been taken into account. A calibrated 25 ml. burette was used in the titrations. All pipettes and measuring flasks were also calibrated.

The reagents were dissolved in water to make 0.2, 0.1, 0.05 and 0.02 normal solutions. 10 ml. of the solution to be titrated were placed in the titration vessel and the proper reagent of approximately the same strength added, a few ml. at a time until about 90% of the reaction was completed as determined by a preliminary experiment. The reagent was then added a few drops at a time and finally dropwise until a clear excess of about 1 ml. had been added. The solution was stirred after each addition

and the E.M.F. of the cell noted after equilibrium had been reached, as shown by the constancy of the E.M.F. to within ± 1 mV.

In the following tables, the results of titrations of $N/5$ and $N/50$ solutions only have been given, while those of the intermediate concentrations, being of similar nature, have been omitted. The end-points have been found out from the maximum value of the rate of change of the E.M.F. with the amounts of the reagent added. The results in each case have been compared with the analytical data. In the tables E is expressed in volts and dE in millivolts.

TABLE I

Estimation of lead with sodium sulphate as the precipitant.

9.88 ml. $Pb(NO_3)_2$ + no alcohol			9.88 ml. $Pb(NO_3)_2$ + 10 ml alcohol.		
V.	E.	dE/dV .	V.	E.	dE/dV .
		(mV/ml.)			(mV/ml.)
(i) With 1.067 $N/5-Na_2SO_4$.					
0 ml.	0.391 volt		0 ml.	0.393 volt	
5	.411	4	5	.413	4
8	.433	7*	8	.432	6
8.5	.443	20	8.8	.445	16
8.8	.454	37	9.0	.455	50
9.0	.465	55	9.2	.469	70
9.2	.479	70	9.3	.508	390
9.3	.488	90	9.4	.520	120
9.5	.493	25	9.5	.526	60
10.0	.502	18	10.0	.531	10
End-point: 9.25 ml. Pb = 0.020688 g./ml.			End-point: 9.25 ml. Pb = 0.020688 g./ml.		
(Gravimetric value: 0.020751 g./ml.)					
(ii) With 1.0674 $N/50-Na_2SO_4$.					
0 ml.	0.430 volt		0 ml.	0.401 volt	
5	.443	3	6	.431	5
8	.462	6	8	.453	11
8.5	.466	8	8.8	.470	21
9.0	.473	14	9.0	.478	40
9.2	.480	35	9.2	.490	60
9.3	.483	30	9.3	.500	100
9.4	.485	20	9.4	.504	40
9.8	.490	12	9.7	.507	10
10.0	.491	5	10.0	.509	7
End point: 9.2 ml. Pb = 0.002059 g./ml.			End point: 9.25 ml. Pb = 0.00207 g./ml.		
(Gravimetric value: 0.002073 g./ml.)					

* Approximated to the nearest unit.

TABLE II

Estimation of lead with sodium oxalate as the precipitant.

10 ml. Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + no alcohol.			10 ml. Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + 10 ml. alcohol.		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
(i) With 1.0014 N/5-Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .					
0 ml.	0.395 volt		0 ml.	0.391 volt	
6	.418	4	5	.407	3
9	.440	7	9	.432	6
9.8	.472	40	9.7	.451	27
9.9	.490	180	9.9	.470	95
10.0	.531	410	10.0	.500	300
10.1	.543	120	10.1	.556	560
10.2	.549	60	10.2	.565	90
10.5	.561	40	10.3	.570	50
11.0	.572	22	10.6	.582	40
End point: 9.95 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.020645 g./ml.			End point: 10.05 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.02085 g./ml.		
(ii) With 1.0002 N/50-Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄ .					
0 ml.	0.428 volt	2	0 ml.	0.403 volt	3
6	.442	7	6	.423	12
9	.462	20	9	.459	54
9.5	.472	40	9.5	.486	120
9.8	.484	80	9.8	.522	140
9.9	.492	140	9.9	.536	220
10.0	.506	90	10.0	.558	140
10.1	.515	50	10.1	.572	70
10.3	.586		10.3	.586	
End-point: 9.95 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.002062 g./ml.			End-point: 9.95 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.002062 g./ml.		

TABLE III

*Estimation of lead with potassium chromate as the precipitant.*Pb(NO₃)₂ = 9.88 ml. Alcohol - nil.

(i) With 1.0320 N/5-K ₂ CrO ₄ .			(ii) With 1.0297 N/50-K ₂ CrO ₄ .		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
0 ml.	0.395 volt	3	0 ml.	0.420 volt	
6	.415	9	6	.437	3
9	.443	30	9	.470	11
9.2	.449	45	9.2	.478	40
9.4	.458	90	9.4	.490	60
9.5	.467	360	9.5	.499	90
9.55	.503	(unsteady)	9.55	.506	140
9.6	.461	"	9.6	.515	180
9.8	...	"	9.7	.525	100
10.0	...	"	9.8	.488	(unsteady)
			10.0	...	"
End-point: 9.55 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.020665 g./ml. Grav. value = 0.020751 g./ml.			End-point = 9.6 ml. Pb ⁺⁺ = 0.002072 g./ml. Grav. value = 0.002073 g./ml.		

TABLE IV

Estimation of sulphate with lead nitrate as the precipitant.

(i) With $Pb(NO_3)_2=1.0015N/5$.

10 ml. Na_2SO_4 without alcohol.			10 ml. Na_2SO_4 with 10 ml. alcohol.		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
0 ml.	0.544 volt	3	0 ml.	0.562 volts.	3
6	.528	5	6	.547	5
9	.512	6	9.0	.532	12
9.5	.509	24	9.5	.526	23
9.75	.503	52	9.8	.519	55
10.0	.490	80	10.0	.508	100
10.1	.482	80	10.1	.498	320
10.2	.474	60	10.2	.466	140
10.3	.468	40	10.3	.452	45
10.5	.460		10.5	.443	
End-point: 10.15 ml. $SO_4^{2-}=0.009763$ g./ml.			End-point: 10.15 ml. $SO_4^{2-}=0.009763$ g./ml.		

(ii) With 0.9986 N/20 $Pb(NO_3)_2$ *

0 ml.	0.525 volt	2	0 ml.	0.547 volt	3
6	.513	2	6	.532	3
9	.508	8	9	.517	10
9.5	.504	15	9.5	.512	23
9.9	.498	30	9.9	.503	30
10.0	.495	40	10.0	.500	50
10.1	.491	40	10.1	.495	140
10.2	.487	20	10.2	.481	50
10.3	.485	7	10.3	.476	17
10.6	.483		10.6	.471	
End point = 10.15 ml. $SO_4^{2-}=0.002435$ g./ml.					
Grav. value = 0.002428 g./ml.					

* Titrations with N/50 solutions gave unsatisfactory results

TABLE V

Estimation of sulphate with barium chloride as the precipitant.

$BaCl_2=1.0025N/10$. * $Pb(NO_3)_2=$ approx. N/10.

10 ml. $Na_2SO_4+0.025$ ml. $Pb(SO_4)_2$ +no alcohol.			10 ml. $Na_2SO_4+0.025$ ml. $Pb(NO_3)_2$ +10ml. alcohol.		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
0 ml.	0.547 volt	1	0 ml.	0.570 volt	2
4	.543	0	6	.561	1
8	.542	7	9	.557	5
9	.535	10	9.6	.554	20
9.5	.530	13	9.8	.550	40
9.8	.526	30	10.0	.542	130
9.9	.523	50	10.1	.529	10
10.0	.518	20	10.2	.528	10
10.1	.516	10	10.3	.527	5
10.2	.515	7	10.5	.526	
10.5	.513				

End-point: (9.95-0.025)=9.925 ml.

End-point: (10.05-0.025)=10.025 ml.

$SO_4^{2-}=0.004779$ g./ml. (Gravimetric value=0.004860 g./ml.) $SO_4^{2-}=0.004811$ g./ml.

* Results of titrations with only one dilution is given as a representative set of data.

TABLE VI

Estimation of barium with sodium sulphate as the precipitant.(i) With 1.0666N/5-Na₂SO₄ and N/5(approx.) Pb(NO₃)₂.

9.88 ml. BaCl ₂ +0.1 ml Pb(NO ₃) ₂ without alcohol.			9.88 ml. BaCl ₂ +0.1 ml. Pb(NO ₃) ₂ + 10 ml. alcohol.		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
0 ml.	0.457 volt	4	0 ml.	0.462 volt	3
7	.483	3	6	.479	4
10.5	.493	4	9	.490	1
11.0	.495	1	10.5	.492	2
11.2	.497	15	11.0	.493	3
11.4	.500	140	11.3	.494	30
11.5	.514	20	11.5	.500	110
11.6	.516	5	11.6	.511	40
12.0	.518		11.8	.519	2
			12.0	.522	

End-point: (11.45-0.1)=11.35 ml.

Ba''=0.016830 g./ml. (Gravimetric value: 0.016954 g./ml.)

End-point: (11.55-0.1)=11.45 ml.

Ba''=0.016978 g./ml.

(ii) With 1.0674N/50-Na₂SO₄ and approx. N/50-Pb(NO₃)₂.

0 ml. 0.490 volt			0 ml. 0.470 volt		
V.	E.	dE/dV.	V.	E.	dE/dV.
0 ml.	0.490 volt	1	0 ml.	0.470 volt	0
6	.496	0	6	.471	0
10	.496	1	10	.472	6
11	.497	3	11	.478	10
11.3	.498	30	11.3	.481	45
11.4	.501	70	11.5	.490	270
11.5	.508	40	11.6	.517	10
11.6	.512	20	11.7	.518	7
11.8	.516	5	12.0	.520	
12.0	.515				

End-point: (11.45-0.1)=11.35 ml.

Ba''=0.001684 g./ml. (Gravimetric value: 0.001692 g./ml.)

End-point: (11.55-0.1)=11.45 ml.

Ba''=0.001700 g./ml.

DISCUSSION

It will appear from the data recorded in Tables I-III that the estimation of lead can be made satisfactorily by potentiometric titration, using the lead amalgam electrode and standard solutions of sodium sulphate or oxalate or potassium chromate. In the first case, the addition of an equal volume of ethyl alcohol (absolute) raises the dE/dV values near the end-point and therefore, increases the sensitivity of the process. In the case of oxalate, high dE/dV values are obtained near the end-point even without the addition of alcohol. In titrating lead salts with potassium chromate, however, the electrode ceases to give reproducible values of the electrode potential at or soon after the end-point is reached, owing, perhaps, to the action of the chromate on the lead in the amalgam (Table III). The addition of alcohol does not produce any improvement (the data for which have been omitted.)

The titration of sodium sulphate with lead nitrate gives good results only if alcohol is added previously and the solution is not too dilute. In the case of titrations with barium chloride, however, the results are low by about 1%.

The titrations of barium chloride with sodium sulphate is satisfactory. The addition of alcohol becomes necessary when the solutions are dilute.

From the facts recorded above, it may be concluded that a two-phase lead amalgam forms a reversible indicator electrode under suitable experimental conditions. This is in agreement with the observations of Denina and Caris (*loc. cit.*).

As already stated, two forms of the electrode vessels have been used. Electrode (I) requires less care in handling and titrations may be performed even with a small volume of the solution. It suffers from the disadvantage that the precipitate formed during the titration settles on the surface of the amalgam causing some delay in the attainment of equilibrium and necessitating frequent stirring. Electrode (II), although requiring more care in handling in order that the amalgam may not be thrown out of its place during stirring, does not suffer from this disadvantage. A clean surface of the amalgam is always exposed to the solution and equilibrium is rapidly attained. Moreover, the titration vessel may be kept in a thermostat, if necessary.

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